

The Degree of Study of Numerals by Scientists in the World

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ABSTRACT. Numerals are used in a variety of tasks, both in science and in everyday life. Using numbers, we record the results of calculations (twenty, forty years), determine the order between the elements of the plural (the first speaker, the millionth person to live), and express the results of the measurement of something (a mile and a half). In addition, numeric characters can be used instead of words, letters, for example, to encode text.

Chinese culture is recognized as one of the oldest written cultures. Yu. M. Lotman considers writing to be one of the forms of memory. In this sense, history can be interpreted as an "additional consequence of the emergence of writing". "While written culture is about the past, oral culture is about the future. That's why predictions, divination and predictions played a big role in it. "According to the scientist, "the world of verbal memory is full of symbols", the material is included in the list of objects and is included in the text of ceremonies, not in the text consisting of words. In the written culture, however, the situation is different. Such a culture "seeks to see the Text created by God or Nature, to read the message expressed in it." Numbers play an important role in this "reading of the world-text" by the Chinese. According to A. Karapetyants's Great Dictionary of the Chinese Language (中文大辞典 zhōngwén dà cídiǎn 1962-1968), there are 13,296 dictionary articles beginning with numbers.

KEYWORDS: China, numbers, linguistics, lexicology, grammatica, Chinese grammar, European grammars.

INTRODUCTION

The study of language in China began 2000 years ago and developed independently until the end of the nineteenth century, with little regard for the influence of Indian science. The peculiarity of classical Chinese linguistics is that it is based on a language that is written in a non-inflected, hieroglyphic script. [Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary. edited by V. N. Yartseva, - Moscow: "Soviet encyclopedia", 1990, P. 222.] Naturally, therefore, in the Chinese language tradition, the hieroglyph, its reading and meaning, was chosen as the main object, while the most advanced branches of linguistics were writing (graphics), lexicology, and phonetics. The first classical scholar of Chinese linguistics, Xu Shen (1st century AD), proposed a classification of hieroglyphs and separated their components. In the III-VI centuries dictionaries of homophones and rhymes were created and tones were described.

THE MAIN RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Due to the isolated nature of the Chinese language, the development of grammar was far behind. The grammatical study of the Chinese language began in the late 19th century, with the publication in 1898 of the grammar of Ma Jian Chun (马建忠 mǎjiànzhōng) "Mashi venton (马氏文通 mǎshìwéntōng)" [Kiryukhina L. V. Syntactic studies of the Chinese grammarian MA Jianzhong. Bulletin of the Buryat state University.-Tambov. Diploma, 2016. no. 6(60) in 3 h. CH.1.-P. 117-120.]. Previously, however, grammar research in China did not deviate from the European sphere of influence. Hence, Chinese grammar was originally based on examples of traditional European grammars. Naturally, such an approach focused on the general characteristics of languages, but did not pay enough attention to the specific features of the Chinese language, in particular, a separate method of expressing the semantics of quantity (numbers) - arithmetic (classifiers). Uzbek Chinese scholar A. Karimov writes about this topic in his monograph: "Accounting, as a rule, cannot come as independent parts of speech. In special cases, they may come as a determinant [Karimov A.A. Chinese-language calculus words: lexical-semantic, functional analysis.- T.: Science and technology, 2003.-P.108.]. Numbers, like arithmetic, can rarely be parts of speech. Quantitative combinations formed from the combination of the word number and arithmetic can easily come in different functions in speech.

Wan Li (王力 wánglì) is a scholar who has made an invaluable contribution to the study of Chinese grammar. Beginning in 1922, he began to seriously study the grammar of the Chinese language. A clear example of this is the dissertation "Grammar of Ancient

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Chinese Texts" (中国古语法 "zhōngguó gǔwén fǎ "), defended in 1926 at Tsing Hua University. In the 1930s, he wrote "The Experience of Thinking on the Grammar of the Chinese Language" (中国文法学初探 "zhōngguó wén fǎxué chūtàn"[王力. 中国文法学初探.:山西人民出版社,2014.-204 页], 1936 (reprinted in 2014)), "New Ways to Learn Chinese Grammar" (中国语法学多新办法"zhōngguó yǔfǎ xué duō xīn bànfǎ"[王力.中国语法学的新途径.-北京,1939 年.-120 页], 1939) revealed the peculiarities of language grammar. In the 1940s, his fundamental works were "Grammar of Modern Chinese" (中国现代语法 "zhōngguó xiàndài yǔfǎ"[王力. 中国现代语法.北京.商务印书馆.1985.423 页], 1943-1944 reprinted in 1985), "Theory of Chinese Grammar" (中国语法理论"zhōngguó yǔfǎ lǐlùn"[王力.中国语法理论.-北京.:中华书局,2015.-311 页], 1944-1945 (revised in 2015). published)), "Fundamentals of Chinese Grammar" (中国语法纲要"zhōngguó yǔfǎ gāngyào"[王力.中国语法纲要.-上海.:上海教育出版社,1982.181 页], 1946 (reprinted in 1982)) saw the world.

Wan Li 's scientific treatises on creativity and Chinese grammar were published by A.A. Dragunov, A.L. Studied by Russian Chinese scholars such as Semen, V.M Solntsev[Dragunov, A. A., Preface//Wan Liao And Fundamentals of Chinese grammar. - Moscow: Iz-vo foreign literature, 1954. -262 p.;Semen A. L. Linguistic research in China//Questions of linguistics. - Moscow, 1988, No. 1, - P. 132-14.;

Solntsev V. M. the Problem of parts of speech in Chinese jazykem the works of linguists China//Questions of linguistics, Moscow, 1955, No. 5, Pp. 105-116.].

Wan Li plays a central role in the grammatical system, syntax. While studying Chinese word groups, he emphasizes number word grouping. According to him, "There are specific difficulties in learning numbers in Chinese. Because the system of quantitative numbers in Chinese is completely different [王力. 中国现代语法.北京.:商务印书馆.1985.-224 页]. Wan Li was of the opinion that the grammatical problems of speech are inherent in him, given the difficulty of the Chinese language according to the level of learning.

Modern Chinese grammar scholars Zhang Chi Cheng and Zhang Yan Shen studied the field of numerology related to Chinese numbers. In his work, Zhang Chi Chen studied the history of the development of numerology in China more. In particular, he dealt with the methodology of the field of numerology in Ancient Chinese sources, revealing aspects of the relation of classificationism to numerology. Zhang Yan Shen, on the other hand, studied the semantics of numbers, the proportionality of basic numerological numbers and symbols. Their work has made a significant contribution to the field of numerology [张其成.象数易学. 广西科学技术出版社., 2009 年.356 页; 张延生“象数易学与逻辑”北京,中央编译出版社 2015 年].

A.A. Dragunov, a representative of the Russian School of Chinese Studies, agreed with Wan Li's views on this phrase, focusing on the study of more ordinal numbers. numerological numbers have at least two ontological values comparable to the difference between quantitative and ordinal numbers ". A distinctive feature of Chinese numbers is the lack of fundamental differences in the formation of their quantitative and orderly forms (for example, in Russian *odin pervy, dva and vtoroy*). As a result of the advent of the prefix "第 dī" along with direct numbers, the formation of ordinal numbers is a relatively new phenomenon[Dragunov A. A. Research on the grammar of modern Chinese. M., 1952. - P. 195.].

As mentioned above, the occurrence of prefixes (prefixes) with numbers in Chinese is a unique phenomenon. AA Khamatova also commented on this: in Chinese, in addition to the prefix 第 dī, there is the prefix 老 lǎo, which is often used to express the relationship of "kinship". For example, 老二 lǎoèr is the second child, 老三 lǎosān is the third child. However, this prefix is not used with multiple morpheme numbers, for example 老十一妹 lǎo shāosānyī mèi is not called the eleventh sister.[Khamatova A. A. word Formation of the modern Chinese language.-Moscow:"Ant", 2003. - C. 184.].

Russian Chinese scholars V.M.Solntseva and N.V.Solntseva were also directly involved in grammar, in their "Teoriticheskaya grammatika sovremennogo kitayskogo yazyka. Problems of morphology. In the book "Course lecture" in the section of word groups gave detailed information about the number of words. In particular, the general classification of numbers in Chinese, their construction, grammatical features are clearly explained [Solntsev V. M., Solntseva N. V. Theoretical grammar of modern Chinese. Problems of morphology.Course of lectures.-Moscow:Military Institute, 1978, P. 152].

Doctor of Philology, Professor A.I Kobzev in his doctoral dissertation "Methodology of Chinese Classical Philosophy (Numerology and Protology)" and in the monograph "Teaching Symbols and Numbers in Chinese Classical Philosophy" study the field of numerology in Chinese. showed that it is important. He has also covered more than a dozen of his articles on the subject. In his works, he skillfully expressed the classical period, that is, the stages of creation and development of the field of numerology in Ancient China, the balance of numbers and symbols in Chinese classical philosophy.[Kobzev A. I. Methodology of Chinese classical philosophy (numerology and protology)". - Aftoref. dis.... doctor of Philology. Moscow, if RAS, 1989, P. 95.; Kobzev A.I. The Doctrine of symbols and numbers in Chinese classical philosophy, Moscow: Nauka, 1994, P. 32.].

In recent years, the science of linguistics has begun to study the issues of language and culture. V.V Vorobyov writes that "today linguistics studies a set of cultural values selected in a certain way, living communicative processes in speech creation and

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perception, linguistic personality experience and national mentality, can be noted as a new philological science that systematically provides a linguistic picture of the world landscape, ensuring the fulfillment of educational, pedagogical and intellectual tasks of education. Thus, linguoculture is a complex science that reflects the interaction and interaction of culture and language, and this process as a whole structure of linguistic and non-linguistic (cultural) units [Vorobyov V. V. on the status of linguoculturology/ /Congress MAPRYAL. Russian language, literature and culture at the turn of the century. T. 2. - Bratislava, 1999. - P. 125-126.].

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Tsui Hong En is a researcher who has made a comparative-typological analysis of the semantics of numbers in Russian and Chinese. In his work, he tried to explain the semantics of numbers in two languages based on the grammatical rules of modern Chinese and Russian [Tsui Hong En. Semantics of number names in the Russian and Chinese languages: linguoculturological aspect. - Aftoref. dis.... Cand. Philol. nauk. - Krasnodar, 2003. - 23C.].

Based on the general description of the Russian and Chinese languages, the researcher in the research work made a comparative study of the semantic field of numbers. The study includes the formation of Chinese number concepts and arithmetic systems, Chinese arithmetic, the separation of numbers in Russian and Chinese as separate word groups, the semantic development of the concept of "number" in Russian and Chinese culture, the use of numbers in bilingual literature and phraseological units focused on issues. Introducing the research, Tsui Hong En wrote: "Thus, we have come to the conclusion that numbers play a greater role in Chinese culture than in Russian."

Wang Min Tsi approached the comparative study of languages from the point of view of the Chinese in terms of the native language of the Chinese and the landscape of the Russian language in the study of number vocabulary. The research work examines and compares the linguistic means of expressing the category of quantity in Russian. In addition, the difficulties encountered in identifying similarities and differences in the category of numbers of two languages, as well as translating from one language to another containing direct or indirect quantitative data examined. Achieving this goal solved the following tasks: 1. Revealed the interdependence of the linguistic elements of quantity expression in Russian and Chinese, their specificity and typological similarity; 2. Identified and described the national and cultural specifics of linguistic means of expressing the category of quantity in Russian and Chinese. 3. Determined how to translate special words (classifiers) of Chinese into Russian. compiled Chinese-Russian and Russian-Chinese bilingual phrases of special units (classifiers, counting words)[Wang Ming Tsi. The expression of number in Russian language: From the position of a native Chinese speaker. Aftoref. dis....kand. filol.nauk. - Penza, 2004. -24 p.]

Representatives of the Uzbek School of Chinese Studies are also studying the issues of numerals in Chinese. Regarding the combination of numbers and arithmetic, AA Karimov said: "Language, in the process of its historical development, uses various means and methods to express any grammatical meaning. Our diachronic study of arithmetic in Wenyang (ancient Chinese) is necessary to better understand the nature and specificity of modern Chinese arithmetic." [Karimov A.A. Chinese-language calculus words: lexical-semantic, functional analysis.- T.: Science and technology, 2003.- P.26.]

The scientist takes a unique approach to the subject and skillfully interprets the fact that numbers in ancient Chinese are directly related to other word groups, especially arithmetic. Model 1. Number+noun (for example, 二人 èrrén two people); Model 2. "noun + number" (for example, 牛一 niúyī one cow, 羊一 yángyī one sheep); Model 3. "noun + number + account" (for example, 马三匹 mǎsān pǐ three horses); Model 4. "number + account + zhī + noun" (for example, 三寸之舌 sāncùn zhī shé sāncùnzhīshé is a master of words. three sun (10cm)); Model 5. "number + account + horse" (for example, 一尺布 yìchǐbù one (meter) cloth.).

The movement also refers to the use of arithmetic in ancient Chinese. They were divided into three models: model 1. "number + verb" (for example, 三鼓 sāngǔ to hit the drum three times); Model 2. "verb + zhě + number" (for example, 坏者三 huài zhě sān has many evils. Literally: evils are three times more); Model 3. "verb + number + arithmetic" (e.g. 读三遍 dú sānbìan to read three times).

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In her research work "Lexical-semantic and structural analysis of diplomatic terms in modern Chinese" S.A. Nosirova commented on the method of abbreviation with the participation of numbers in the construction of diplomatic terms in modern Chinese: "Chinese abbreviations are part of the Chinese lexicon. Among them are abbreviations related to numbers. For example, in one of the models of abbreviations in the style of simple abbreviations, 简称 Jian cheng is used mainly for abbreviations formed by numbers. For example: 一 (二, 三) 秘 Yi (er/ san) mi. Full view: 一 (二, 三) 等秘书 ī (èr, sān) děng mīshū First (second, third) level secretary: number + AV = number A. Or: 一中一台 yizhong yitai Zhōngguó, and a new term was formed as a result of the combination of the first syllables of the words 台湾 taiwan. [Nosirova S. A. Now China tilida diplomatic atamallarning lexik-semantic and structural analysis. T., F. F. n. dissert., 2007. -P.97].

The Chinese national consciousness factor is of primary importance in the creation of many new abbreviations. The widespread use of the cognitive method in the formation of new terms in Chinese can also be seen using the following examples. For example, if we take the example of 两个中国 liangge zhongguo, the literal translation of the term "two Chinese" would certainly cause a lot of misunderstanding, where the translator is certainly cognitive as a factor in Chinese psychology, a factor of national consciousness. should be approached from a linguistic point of view, only then will it be possible to give a correct translation of the term, including "PRC with two systems". Or a few other examples: 三大作风 sanda zuofeng three different "style" (理论和实践相结合的作风, 和人民群众紧密地联系在一起的作风, 批评和自我批评的作风 lilun he shijian xiangjiehede zuofeng, he renmin jinmide lianxi zaiyiqide zuofeng, piping he ziwo pipingde zuofeng) a combination of theory and practice, public association and criticism, methods of self-criticism); 两个文明 lianggewenming "two cultures" (shèhuìzhǔyì wùzhìwénmíng, " (社会主义物质文明, 社会主义精神文明 shehui zhuyi wuzhi wenming, shehui zhuyi jingshen wenming), 三个面向 sange mianxiang "to face three things" (面向现代化, 面向世界, 面向未来 mianxiang xiandaihua, mianxiang shijie, mianxiang weilai modernization).

However, it is safe to say that in the lexical layer of modern Chinese, the number of new terms formed by the abbreviation method, including those related to numbers, is increasing.

Structural and functional analysis of reduplicative units in various word categories in modern Chinese, especially in the number word group in revealing the features of reduplicative word models S. Hashimova's research is unique. Analyzing the work of the scientist, we saw 3 reduplicative models of number and arithmetic: "AA", "yī — AA", "yī — A yī — A". The "AA" form of counting words is usually one of the most common repetitive patterns, and a word with this reduplicative form means "everyone". The appearance of "ī — AA" differs from the above model by the addition of the number one, which means many. The yī — A yī — A model is a completely repetitive form of the number and arithmetic phrase [Khashimova S. The A.Reduplication in the current Chinese language. The elephant.science.Nomz...the DIS.Authorship.-, 2009.-P .24.].

There is no section or chapter on number reduplication in the study. Focusing on the grammatical functions of repeated quantitative-numerical combinations, the formation of quantitative combinations using the word and number together is shown in detail. It is clearly stated that they can be repeated individually within the compound. [Hoshimova S. The A.Reduplication in the current Chinese language.- : "Navruz" Publishing House, 2017.- P.80.] For example:

1. A word in a quantitative compound can be repeated separately. Usually, the number "one" is often repeated, meaning "everyone" and serves as a case in point: 一一握手 yīyīwòshǒu shakes hands one by one.
2. In a quantitative combination, both a number and an arithmetic can be repeated at the same time. If they serve as a determinant, they are of course 的 de added: : 一盘一盘的水果 yī pán yī pán de shuǐguǒ partially wet fruits.
3. In a repeated quantitative combination, the number "one" may be dropped, but not after the quantitative combination: 这时候件件事又涌上心头 zhè shí hòu jiàn jiàn wǎng shìyòu tǒng shàng xīn tóu.
4. Double quantitative compounds can occur as a case function. In doing so, they mean "in sequence": 两个两个地 liǎng gèliǎng gè dì liǎnggè liǎnggè de .
5. If the number "one" is omitted in the repeated quantitative combination, then de de is not set: 天气一天天暖和起来了 Tiānqì yī tiāntiān nuǎnhé qǐlái le . The weather began to heat up day by day.

In addition, according to the scientist, there is the formation of reduplicative models in the section of verbs using numbers. For example: 看一看 kànyīkàn to see, a word meaning to see. This case is a model of reduplicative verbs, and the number is an integral part of it. As a rule, numbers other than one number ī yī cannot be used. Other numbers may also be hesitant independently, but they retain their pure meaning. For example: 三三个 sān sāngè . In this case, the word does not have a reduplicative form, only a pair of words, which have a repetitive form.

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Hoshimova S.A. in the research work it can be understood that on the basis of the table given the mutual percentage of complete and incomplete models of Chinese language group reduplication and analyzed the occurrence of equal and incomplete reduplicative models in horse, quality, number word groups.

While observing the research work of Uzbek Chinese scholars, in the monograph "Formation and development of the system of Chinese linguistic terms" by Mustafaeva S., we came across numerical aspects in the construction and structural features of Chinese linguistic terms. The scholar believes that the second major method after the compositional method in Chinese word formation is the affixation method. According to him, the prefix 第 *dì* from Chinese prefixes, 反 *fǎn* "anti" -, "counter" - is used in the construction of linguistic terms: prefix + *yī* "one" 第一人称 (身) *dìyīrénchēng* (shēn) "person"; 第三格 *Disān gé disāngé* "third agreement" *ǎdì* comes as a prefix + *sān* "three" + *gé* "agreement" "[Mustafayev S. T. China tili milishnikov of terminology, formatting and development: Monograph-T.: "Vostok", 2016. - P. 86.].

According to Mustafaeva, although the affixation method is one of the leading forms of Chinese word formation, it is not as productive in the formation of terms in the field of linguistics.

Numerical issues are partially covered in the textbook "Introduction to Chinese Philology" and practical issues are covered in the textbook "Chinese". In it we have given a general description of numbers, and in the classification of numbers we have tried to give information such as incremental numbers, fractional numbers, percentage numbers, approximate numbers, the construction of numbers, and the grammatical properties of numbers. The semantic properties of numbers have not been studied. However, since the collected materials are important in illuminating the number word series in Chinese, we have been using them in our research work. [Mavlyanova U.X.Nazirova Sh.M. Introduction to Chinese Philology.-T. : TashDShI, 2018.-170 p.;Mavlyanova U.X.Chinese.-T.:TashDShI, 2017.-304 p.]

CONCLUSION

With this in mind, one of the most conservative parts of the language system, the numerical phrase, was chosen as the source of the study. This is due to the fact that for the first time in the field of numerology in Chinese monograph analysis of the proportions of numbers and symbols, revealing the national and cultural features of numbers in Chinese discourse, analyzing the linguocultural features of numbers in Chinese.

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